

Proceeding Paper

Effects of self-generated versus scaffolded concept maps on STEM learning

Samuel Aina* and Olusola Adesope*

MERIT Lab, Department of Educational Psychology and Kinesiology, Washington State University, Pullman, Washington State, USA

* Correspondence: samuel.aina@wsu.edu; olusola.adesope@wsu.edu

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Abstract

Although there is overwhelming research evidence showing that generative activities such as self-generated concept maps are better for student learning than researcher or educator-generated concept maps, little is known about how fully self-generated and partially-generated concept maps activities influence student learning outcomes. Using data from 590 undergraduate students enrolled in a first-year chemistry course at a Pacific Northwest university in the United States, we explored the relative effectiveness of asking students to fully self-generate a concept map versus giving them a scaffolded concept map to fill in. The results revealed no significant overall main effect of concept map condition, we concluded with a recommendation for future studies.

Keywords: Self-generated map, scaffolded map, concept map, STEM, learning.

Statement of the Problem

Generative activities such as concept maps entail asking students to create new knowledge, construct an artifact or demonstrate conceptual understanding rather than regurgitating facts. Although there is overwhelming research evidence showing that generative activities such as self-generated concept maps are better for student learning than researcher or educator-generated concept maps (Nesbit & Adesope, 2006; Schroeder et al, 2018; Fiorella & Mayer, 2015), little is known about how fully self-generated and partially-generated concept maps activities influence student learning outcomes.

A primary objective of the present study is to extend the concept map literature and explore the relative effectiveness of asking students to fully self-generate a concept map versus giving them a scaffolded concept map to fill in. The present study seeks to understand the effects of learning with two different concept map materials: (a) self-generated concept map; and (b) scaffolded concept map.

Participants

Five hundred and ninety undergraduate students enrolled in a first-year chemistry course at a Pacific Northwest university in the United States participated in the study. Data from students enrolled in two sessions of the course (8am and 1pm) were collected for the present study.

Procedure

Students in the self-generated group were given 12 key chemistry concepts on enthalpy to construct a concept map. In comparison, students in the scaffolded group were given a concept map with four of those 12 concepts already filled in, leaving them to fill in the remaining twelve key concepts. Dependent measures for the study include immediate posttest and delayed retention questions. Independent-samples *t*-test and one-way within-group ANOVA were used for analysis.

Results

A multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) was used to compare the effect of self-generated versus scaffolded concept maps on students' recall and retention of chemistry concepts, while controlling for pretest. The results revealed no significant overall main effect of concept map condition, Wilks' $\lambda = .996$, $F(2, 586) = 1.17$, $p = .31$, $\eta_p^2 = .004$. Both self-generated and scaffolded concept map groups did not significantly differ on recall and retention.

For the scaffolded within-group effect, a one-way within-groups ANOVA revealed a significant effect of learning with scaffolded concept map, $F(1.59, 534) = 933.71$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .74$. Follow-up comparisons using the Bonferroni test indicate participants had significantly higher scores on posttest recall ($M = 4.84$, $SD = 1.98$) than at pretest ($M = 1.40$, $SD = 0.99$) and

retention ($M = 1.16$, $SD = 0.75$). However, participants had significantly lower scores on posttest retention than pretest ($p = .001$).

For self-generated within-group effect, a one-way within-groups ANOVA revealed a significant effect of learning with scaffolded concept map on learning, $F(1.45, 367.08) = 635.24$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .72$. Follow-up comparisons using the Bonferroni test indicate participants had significantly higher scores on posttest recall ($M = 4.86$, $SD = 2.15$) than on pretest ($M = 1.35$, $SD = 0.96$) and retention ($M = 1.26$, $SD = 0.75$). The difference between pretest scores and retention scores was not statistically significant ($p = .65$).

Conclusion

The results of this study suggest that scaffolded concept map activities is as effective as self-generated maps. Both scaffolded and self-generated concept maps help students in better recalling chemistry concepts. Future studies should examine the effect of gradually removing scaffolding.

References

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